

The Motivational Role of Educators in terms of Social Support from the School Principal and Other Colleagues at Work

Safiye Topdemir

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Prof. Sabrina Corbi

1

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PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS:
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Abstract

The process of integrating a new teacher into the school unit requires a number of phases, one of which is giving the new teacher with social support. According to the findings of

2

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Stavropoulos (2013), the sentiments that teachers experience when they contemplate leaving their present unit or transferring to a new unit are highly influenced by the function of social support from the school principal and other colleagues in the workplace. However, new replacement teachers in Greek public school units are often unsatisfied with the degree of recognition and appreciation they get from their colleagues, as well as the level of professional and social support they receive from the environment of the school. This is especially true of the level of assistance they receive from their colleagues. Principals and parents of students are also unsatisfied with the degree of professional and social support that their children get from the school environment. This discontent extends to the level of assistance that instructors offer for their kids. This dissatisfaction is more likely to take place at institutions that have a larger overall student body and more beginning teachers who may benefit from receiving counseling support. This problem can be improved with the assistance of a professional. In spite of the significance of providing replacement instructors with assistance and direction, the actual educational system does not adhere to every standardized teaching strategy. The pleasure of both parties, as well as their continuing employment at the school, as well as their level of dedication to the learning process, are directly correlated to the quality of the connection that exists between the school principal and the new substitute teacher. Peer counseling is an informal activity that may be interpreted in a variety of different ways depending on the school unit in which it is being carried out. The institutionalization of teacher advice in public schools has not yet been achieved. In a more casual environment, newly hired substitute instructors might get help in a number of different ways. It is acknowledged that leadership plays an important role in providing mentorship, support, and assistance for new substitute teachers at schools, and that administrators of such schools have good views regarding the adoption of programs like these.

Keywords: *Educator Profession, School Principals, Other Incoming Social Support in the Education Community, Educational Sciences and Educational Administration, Educators and Motivation*

CURRENT SCIENCE

Introduction

In spite of the absence of a formal mentoring program, it is essential to find out whether or if there is an unofficial type of assistance available in the form of mentoring. Educational institutions have a responsibility to figure out how to assist students in the manner that will be most beneficial to them. This suggests that there is a growing desire for a mentorship program that is not just organized but also focused on the future. This study's major objective is to determine whether or whether new teachers working in schools are supplied with mentorship support and advice, even though they are physically present in the schools in which they are employed. The purpose of this study is to investigate the role that leadership plays in the mentoring and support process. More specifically, the study focuses on determining the extent to which new teachers get informal advice, support, and direction from colleagues and school administrators. The research also investigates the connection between the leader of the principal's office and the impressions that newly recruited substitute teachers have of the informal assistance and direction that they get from their more experienced colleagues. We employed a quantitative research technique, and the participants filled out questionnaires that they were responsible for giving to themselves and completing. For the collection of the data, a non-probabilistic design was used, and a suitable sample, also known as fit sampling, was selected. Because of their geographical position, the researchers were able to carry out easy sampling and had direct access to primary school teachers who were already part of their networks. Throughout the whole of the process, descriptive and inductive statistics were used. Additionally, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was carried out in order to evaluate the efficiency of the parametric control. As a result of the increased need for substitute teachers brought about by the educational system, the vast majority of the teaching professionals included in the sample had substantial prior experience working in elementary education. This results in the nation's public school systems hiring thousands of extra substitute teachers each and every year to fill up the teaching vacancies. Specific scales have, of course, been used in the research that has been conducted in order to evaluate the level of internal credibility that is linked with mentoring, as well as to measure the perspectives of the teachers about the informal guidance help supplied by the principle and the different leadership styles that are utilized by the principal.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The purpose of this research was to determine the level of internal credibility that is connected with mentoring and the aid that is provided via mentoring. The scale was selected because it is extensively used and recognized in the worldwide arena. Additionally, the scale correctly represents the leadership characteristics of school administrators, which was another important factor in its selection. Included in the evaluation of secondary behaviors by the scale are acts that are helpful, directive, and restricting.

The "director" subscale is the first one, and it places an emphasis on leadership by providing very explicit instructions to the trainers and without allowing them much leeway to use their own judgement. The second kind of leadership, known as "restrictive" leadership, places all of the responsibility on the principal rather than delegating any authority to newly recruited substitute teachers and does not provide them any discretionary authority. The 'supporter' is the third component, and they provide new trainers not just psychological support but also a variety of additional services. Leadership that is authoritative lends a hand to those around them, while leadership that is supportive is more approachable. A directing principal's duties include the provision of helpful criticism, the identification, correction, and explanation of errors made by other instructors, as well as the periodic supervision and direction of the work performed by these teachers.

The first thing that should be taken into consideration is the amount of informal coaching, support, and advice that newly hired substitute teachers get from their colleagues and the administration. According to the comments of those who were polled, there are "several times" when the offer is made to the latter. According to the findings of recent studies, mentoring is an essential element in the procedure of establishing and sustaining a productive and collaborative learning culture at educational institutions. It is crucial for administrators of educational institutions to provide environments that encourage learning and grow their employees. This may be accomplished via the use of a range of approaches, including the provision of mentoring by school authorities, the establishment of school-based education mentoring, and the encouragement of cooperation and collaboration among staff members. The findings indicate that a new substitute teacher does not satisfy all of the parameters necessary for success, as well as that informal mentorship among peers and the mentoring assistance supplied by the school administration are

CURRENT SCIENCE

not utilised to a high degree. Because the level of mentoring aid and guidance supplied to the principle is not very high and is not acceptable in any way, classmates and the administrator tend to take a neutral posture toward new students at the school. This realization came about as a result of the fact that the guidance and assistance provided by the mentor to the mentee turned out to be completely inappropriate.

The results of this study seem to be in line with the findings of prior research that shown a favorable correlation between mentoring assistance from colleagues and mentoring support from school officials. However, what is known as supportive leadership is a type of management that is essential to the effective running of these initiatives. This style of leadership actively promotes the mentoring and assistance of new instructors in educational institutions.

The replies of teachers suggest that there is a supportive atmosphere for mentoring from both the principal and colleagues; the second group is often more supportive than the first. This finding suggests that training programs for administrators should be able to satisfy the need that the school set aside space for continued professional development as well as support for staff members. The primary responsibility of managers should not be dealing with paperwork and other administrative issues; rather, their attention should be directed on assisting employees.

In addition, the relevant rules need to be brought up to date in order to ensure that the responsibilities and obligations of mentoring are met in the most effective manner possible by a teaching staff that is both experienced and certified. Due to the limits placed on the study in terms of both the sample size and the selection method, the findings are restricted to a certain school classification and the working procedures of the personnel that is employed at that school.

Mentoring is a crucial part of the process that must be carried out in order to establish and sustain an environment conducive to effective and cooperative learning. The study investigates the several areas of competence that managers possess, as well as their attitudes on learning and development, their contributions to learning and development, professional learning activities, mentoring roles, learning hurdles, and self-evaluation and benefits. The provision of a sustainable learning environment may be accomplished by school administrators via the use of a range of

CURRENT SCIENCE

resources; mentorship provided by school employees is one of the most effective ways among all of these many approaches.

In a nutshell, the findings of the research emphasize the significance of productive mentoring in establishing an academic setting that encourages fruitful collaboration among students. Researchers are able to reach more relevant findings and have a greater impact on education policy in a broad range of contexts if they center their attention on the points of view of educators working in elementary and secondary schools. Mentoring is an extremely important component in the process of establishing learning objectives, fostering progress, and reiterating to clients that they are responsible for their own education. The director or administrator of an educational institution is the most essential character in this game because he places a significant burden on all facets of the organization that the educational institution represents. According to findings from a study that was carried out by Tahir, Said, Daud, Vazhathodi, and Khan (2016), mentoring significantly improves professional values as school leaders and cultivates a culture of knowledge sharing, both of which contribute to an improvement in the overall levels of self-confidence and self-confidence that are held by school principals.

Methodology

The administration of a school is a difficult position to fill, and newly appointed administrators are required to take part in rigorous training and guidance programs. These programs assist newly appointed administrators in developing a deeper understanding of the organizational culture in which they operate, so enabling them to create learning environments that are both safer and more robust. It is the responsibility of the school administrator to make certain that the institution is effectively managed and is a pioneer in the area of education in order to realize the institution's educational objectives via the effective management of its human and financial resources.

An efficient school administrator is one who is able to create intuitive and novel duties for the school, provide ideal working circumstances for teachers, and educate educators on democratic

CURRENT SCIENCE

participation. These are the three primary responsibilities of an effective school administrator. This strategy offers assistance for trainers as well as opportunities for them to develop professionally. Children are more inclined to participate in schools that emphasize learning via mentorship, which leads to an increase in the amount of information that is retained by the students.

may assist in reducing the pressures that lead to new teachers leaving the profession and guarantee that those instructors remain active in the field. The introduction of a mentoring program into schools may make it possible for experienced school administrators to act in the capacity of mentors to newly hired teachers, so helping to reduce some of the pressures that lead new teachers to quit the field. As more and more studies focus on highly applicable aspects of mentoring, the body of research on mentoring programs for school administrators has started to become more varied. The practice of mentoring is essential for the professional and social growth of school administrators, just as it is for the growth of their workers and the institutions in which they work. On the other hand, not a lot of study has been done in schools to get a better understanding of mentoring and how the mentoring that is supplied by the principle influences the development of a culture that places a high priority on education. In the context of creating a culture of learning in schools, this research investigates the mentoring responsibilities and behaviors of school administrators using a technique that is both inclusive and comprehensive. The investigation was carried out in the form of phenomenological study, and the interviews with the administrators of the schools served as the technique of data collection. The findings that are discussed include the areas of competency that mentor school administrators possess, the perspectives they hold, the contributions they make to learning and development, professional learning activities, the roles that mentoring plays in the creation of a learning culture, and the learning barriers that are encountered in the implementation of mentoring. As a consequence of this, mentoring plays an important part in the process of developing a culture that values learning inside educational institutions. Administrators of educational institutions may make a significant contribution to the overall performance of their organizations by building an atmosphere that is conducive of learning, encouraging self-evaluation and mentorship, and developing a culture that values education. The purpose of this study is to investigate the perspectives of school administrators on mentoring, as well as the development and upkeep of a learning culture in schools. Mentoring is a highly

CURRENT SCIENCE

significant part of education since it assists less experienced colleagues to improve their talents and interests while also offering support and advice for their professional growth. This makes mentoring one of the most important aspects of education. One definition of a mentor is "a patient and experienced person who guides and guides the development of talents and careers in younger people who have less experience."

The concept of a "mentor" has its roots in mythology and developed independently of any particular language in which it was first used. One definition of a mentor is an experienced worker who acts as a guide and director for the development of the skills and careers of less experienced young people entrusted to them in the areas of professional and personal growth. The mentor serves as an example for the apprentice to follow, and shares his expertise and experience with the latter in order to inspire the latter to achieve greater levels of success in his chosen area.

It is generally agreed that mentoring is the single most significant component of an efficient process for professional development. This is due to the fact that it is the first step in boosting the efficiency of learning and teaching across an individual's whole career. In order to assist new teachers in adjusting to the rigors of the teaching profession, school leaders should develop a mentoring network inside their own school. It is well acknowledged that the kind of professional development that yields the best results for educators is one that emphasizes the importance of teamwork and shared expertise among colleagues.

For the objective of the career function to be accomplished, it is necessary for the function to provide assistance and support for the employee's professional growth. This will allow the function to fulfill its mission. Throughout the process of resolving emergent concerns, mentor coaches play a crucial role in maintaining a sense of safety and command for everyone involved. However, as core training programs do not include outstanding content on how to handle professional obstacles, mentoring need to be considered an integral part of the core career development process. Because management training programs are unable to give helpful knowledge on how to cope with the challenges of the profession, it is vital to make mentoring an intrinsic part of the fundamental components of basic career development. Another significant component of mentoring is the psychosocial function that the mentor provides for the mentee. This function helps the mentee develop their identity, as well as their level of competence and their

CURRENT SCIENCE

obligations within the workplace. The less experienced supervisee is responsible for all of these responsibilities, while the more experienced mentor offers both psychological and practical aid. Professional socialization and sponsorship activities, such as introducing the mentee to other colleagues and giving support for the mentee's career, also contribute to the professional assistance offered by the mentors and the client's possibilities for personal and professional growth. Examples of these behaviors include "introducing the mentee to other colleagues" and "offering support for the mentee's career." During the mentoring process, a mentor should demonstrate the client's qualities like mutual trust, understanding, and empathy for one another. One of the most essential traits that must be learned in an educational environment in order to sustain the soundness of the institution is confidence. Confidence is one of the most important qualities that must be mastered. There are a number of critical variables that may contribute to an increase in trust within the school community. One of these things is when principals show their support and appreciation for the job that teachers accomplish.

Professionalism, trust in one another, and respect for one another are the cornerstones of healthy mentoring partnerships. This helps to cultivate an atmosphere that supports the open and honest exchange of ideas, objectives, and other opinions. Mentoring duties are the responsibilities that the mentee places on the mentor within the context of the mentoring relationship. These responsibilities are imposed by the mentee.

In its conclusion, the research stresses the significance of mentorship in the educational system as well as the role that school administrators play in the development and upkeep of a culture that values learning. Schools that cultivate an atmosphere of support in which mentors have the opportunity to develop and thrive are better able to prepare their students for success once they enter the profession. Mentors play an important part in the process of supporting and advocating for students, as well as in developing professional socialization. It is possible to classify them into the following six categories: role based on client interests; role based on mentor's knowledge; role of facilitator; role of confrontation; role of role modeling; and role of supporting the client's vision. Students' professional identities are molded by the mentor's communication of professional goals, modeling of respectable conduct, and role modeling of intellectual stimulation. It is the job of a mentor to encourage positive ideas and sentiments in their mentee, exhibit confidence in the

CURRENT SCIENCE

mentee's own talents, encourage the mentee to take calculated risks, and provide insight into the behavior of the mentee. This results in enhanced learning and greater desire for apprentices to eventually become mentors themselves. The provision of resources is seen as being of the utmost importance by educators who practice knowledge-based instructional conduct, such as teachers and vice principals. It is necessary for school administrators to possess a wide range of abilities in order for them to be successful in their roles as administrators. These skills include conceptual competencies, technical competencies, human competencies, and traditional competencies. These may be broken down into categories such as educational philosophy, management and organizational theories, theories of leadership, technical capabilities, and human competencies. For successful management methods in complex school systems, traditional abilities such as leadership, communication, curriculum design, learning and teaching procedures, and student performance evaluation are crucial.

Kram and Isabella's (1985) definition of mentoring includes professional assistance, psychological support, and role modeling as essential components. This is how mentoring is understood today. According to the findings of research conducted by Lankau and Scandura (2002), the mentee position in the company is able to develop a feeling of success, identity, and competence as a result of these commitments. Creating empathy in human connections, which is one of the aspects of personal growth, and easing emotional bonds are two of the tasks that mentor school administrators are tasked with doing as part of their job responsibilities.

The growth and efficiency of schools may be attributable to a wide range of elements, such as the leadership styles of school administrators, the qualities of teachers, and the school's overall learning capacity. Formal opportunities for students to collaborate are the defining characteristics of an effective learning culture. To support the growth of the school, it is essential to have shared goals that concentrate on uniformly high standards, participatory leadership, and academic assistance, as well as an effective learning culture. An organization that is focused on learning has three essential components: a learning environment that is supportive and contains actual learning processes and practices, supporting leadership behavior, and a supportive learning environment.

As a result, mentoring plays an essential part in fostering a constructive learning environment and contributing to the expansion of educational institutions. Educators may better

CURRENT SCIENCE

help their students and build their professional identities if they have a solid grasp of the duties and responsibilities of mentors. In his article, "The Importance of Learning in Businesses That Have a Solid Learning Culture Inherent in Their DNA," Schein (2010) highlights the significance of learning in firms that have an established learning culture. This "learning gene" is vital for firms that value lifelong learning and adaptation in order for their employees to be able to become more flexible and adaptive. The fundamental characteristics that should be present in a culture that places an emphasis on lifelong education and adaptation are as follows: it is essential to be proactive, to be committed to learning, to believe that the environment can be managed, to be committed to the truth through pragmatism and questioning, to have a hopeful outlook on the future, and to have a clear and complete commitment.

Literature Review

Tichnor Wagner and his colleagues investigated how adults learn about culture by concentrating on adult cooperation, adult learning communities, adult culture of learning, adult culture of learning cultivation, and student culture of learning. In schools where there is a culture that encourages productive learning, there is an emphasis placed on setting high standards for academic achievement among all students. These educational institutions make significant efforts to cultivate a learning culture that, in addition to the students' academic achievements, focuses equal importance on their students' professional and personal growth.

Effective school leaders employ an approach that encourages participation from their students and give encouragement and support for group projects. In addition to that, they use a technique that is participative. Effective instructional leaders are concerned with empowering teachers by engaging them in discourse about their teaching processes, fostering cooperation and collaboration among instructors, and giving teachers with chances for decision-making, autonomy, and self-efficacy in their roles as educators. Within the context of the education program, mentoring activities, which may include a collaborative working culture, have been raised to the status of a priority. They affect both teaching and learning, as well as the relationships between partners, by generating new learning settings and opportunities in the community, and by fostering

CURRENT SCIENCE

an atmosphere that is favorable to the production of innovative ideas and problem solutions. Mentoring and coaching are crucial components of professional development because they contribute to the creation of an environment that sets a high value on learning and stimulate the sharing of information among colleagues. As a result, an environment that places a high value on learning is one that places a high value on mentoring and coaching. It is distinct from other approaches to professional development such as training, management, counseling, and coaching. Among other things. According to Lim (2005), the most essential aspect of mentoring and learning is developing one's leadership skills via interaction with other individuals. The culture of an organization is most significantly impacted when employees are provided with opportunities to participate in activities such as mentoring and coaching. The client may experience increased introspection and clarity of thinking, which may result in increases in psychological well-being and confidence; improvements in problem-solving abilities; gains in practitioner knowledge and skills; enhanced practice sharing; improved communication and relationships; and other advantages.

Because of the increased capacity for introspection that is produced by practical mentoring and coaching techniques, it is imperative that educational institutions give serious consideration to implementing coaching and mentoring activities in the interest of fostering a culture of supportive learning in businesses. Clients who participate in mentoring have the chance to make the shift from independent self-regulation to self-regulation that is guided. Changing the structure, technique, and relationships of partners in a teaching and learning program may have a substantial influence on the mentoring strategy's overall efficacy. This can be accomplished by incorporating a culture of collaboration that is centered on learning and development. Mentoring programs, as well as efforts to improve the effectiveness of lifelong education and education in general, may benefit greatly from the viewpoints of school administrators on education and growth. CEOs who take on the role of educating leaders may enjoy the advantages of mentoring in a variety of different ways. Even though mentoring meetings provide clients and mentors the chance to share their knowledge and experiences with one another, practical experience is still extremely vital for educators to have in order to accomplish the objectives that they have set. Activities that build a feeling of professionalism and contribute to a culture of learning inside an organization are examples of mentoring activities. Schools that engage in mentoring are better able to apply the

CURRENT SCIENCE

knowledge and skills students acquire in that context to other facets of the educational setting. Because senior mentors are more likely to follow school staff members who have had their mentoring experience enhanced and who are overseen by senior mentors, such school staff members are more likely to undergo a more natural metamorphosis.

Mentoring and coaching are strong strategies for influencing and transforming a school's culture, particularly when they are "attuned" to an organization's environment and basic values. This is because these approaches are tailored to the specific needs of the organization. This is particularly important to keep in mind within the context of the collaborative learning environment that a corporation fosters. The practice of mentoring itself includes advantages that accrue to the persons who serve in this capacity. These benefits include enhanced personal satisfaction for mentors who see helping others improve their job performance and the opportunity to share personal experiences that are valuable to colleagues. Because of this, the possibility that mentors will continue to provide aid to others is increased, which ultimately results in the development of the mentoring relationship. According to research conducted by Bolam, McMahon, Pocklington, and Weindling (1995), mentors who take part in a mentoring program enjoy a number of benefits, including the opportunities to communicate with other colleagues, seek professional development, learn about successful and ineffective leadership practices, network with other colleagues, and have knowledge of successful and ineffective leadership practices. Obtain it. greater personal pleasure and greater professional satisfaction are two of the advantages that accrue to a mentor as a consequence of their involvement in the mentoring program. These benefits are one of the benefits that accrue to the mentor. The primary objective of this research is to investigate the parts that school administrators play in the procedure of establishing and cultivating a learning culture in educational institutions, with a focus on the mentoring responsibilities they have and the behaviors they demonstrate to their staff members. For the purpose of this research, phenomenology was selected as the methodological approach, and qualitative research techniques were used for the completion of the study. A phenomenological research has the ability to give light on diverse reactions or views on a phenomena, as Fraenkel and Wallen (2009) note out. This is because of the study's qualitative nature. The phenomenological approach will be used in this study's design since the purpose of the investigation is to uncover the feelings, experiences, and

CURRENT SCIENCE

points of view of school administrators on the growth and establishment of a culture of learning in educational institutions.

Argument

The research was conducted with the involvement of all school administrators in the United States who have at least three years of experience working in the area of school administration. The core of a mentoring relationship is the act of persons with greater expertise offering guidance and assistance to others with less competence in one-on-one or group situations. This may take place in a variety of different contexts. According to the findings of the research, a candidate for a position in school administration should have at least three years of prior experience in the field. This amount of time is regarded enough for having an effect on mentorship and the general learning culture that exists within the institution.

The maximum diversity methodology, which is also known as the diversity in sample selection method, was used in order to elicit a range of perspectives, points of view, and points of view among the participants. In order to do this, representatives were chosen from a wide range of demographic groupings, including gender, level of education, experiences, and kind of school. The amount of women who participated in the research project is clearly reflected in these findings. In Turkey, women make up only 7.2% of school principals. As a result, mentoring and coaching play an essential part in the process of cultivating a culture of learning inside educational institutions and have the ability to dramatically affect the overall performance of school leaders. The purpose of the research was to investigate mentoring relationships and to identify significant recurring patterns that evolved during the mentoring process. In order to collect reliable and accurate data, researchers used a wide range of methods and strategies, such as expert evaluation, triangulation analysis, and in-depth explanations of the perspectives of participants. In order to get more trustworthy outcomes, consistency was also used. The researchers known as authors 2 and 3 each carried out their own separate coding and conceptualization of the data obtained from the individuals. The methodology developed by Miles and Huberman was used in order to ascertain whether or not the codes and conceptualizations created by the two researchers were consistent

CURRENT SCIENCE

with one another. The findings revealed a similarity rate of 84%, which indicates that the coders had reached an agreement.

conceptual, human, and technological competence areas were categorized under the umbrella term "conceptual, human, and technical competence areas" for the administration of guidance schools. These domains put an emphasis on conceptual competence, human competence, and technical competence, respectively. On two issues, participants reached a consensus:

(1) that all stakeholders should have a say in school activities, and

(2) that collaborative management is easier and more successful. They shared their views on the distribution of power, justice, compassion and respect for individuals.

The capacity to have a solid command of the law, to generate finances, to identify and manage company operations, to use technology, and to display professional conduct are all included in the technical competence domain. The findings were compiled under the heading of "learning and development," with coding that placed an emphasis on open learning, adjusting to changing realities, placing value on the learner, learning together, and growing. Participants agreed that a manager should always strive for ongoing self-improvement, be open to continuing training, and be ready to adapt to changing circumstances.

The mentor manager has to show the student appreciation, provide him with suitable chances, learn and grow with all of the workers, and set these behaviors as an example for all of the employees. They also provided the mentor manager with the recommendation that the learning process be directed in a manner that is consistent with a rational work strategy, while maintaining a focus on the mentee's personal growth and development. Being eager to learn something new, not assuming entire responsibility for teaching or developing pupils, and having control over the situation were some of the perspectives expressed by the participants. Learning should be supported, encouraged, given precedence over contributing to learning, led by those who like learning, and led by individuals who enjoy learning. These are the norms of conduct for school administrators.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The viewpoint of one participant on learning and its contribution to development was summed up as follows: if an institution's rate of growth and learning has decreased, it will be difficult for that institution to continue ahead and strive to develop its vision. If an individual is able to learn that enthusiasm while learning, and if the stakeholder is able to see it in the eyes of the learner, then they will be really delighted with this circumstance. The purpose of this research is to investigate the significance of professional learning activities in the formation of a learning culture as well as the influence these activities have on the professional growth of educators. It is broken up into two different categories, which are the assessment of already established professional learning activities and the activities of personal and organizational learning.

Conclusion

Some of the professional development opportunities that have been designated by the administration include in-service trainings, workshops, and seminars that have been presented by the Ministry of National Education (MEB) as well as other organizations within the province. Inadequate programs and non-professional studies, time limits, and management styles that are inhospitable to learning are some of the fundamental criteria that are taken into consideration during the assessment of professional learning activities. According to statements made by administrators of schools, "personal and institutional learning activities" include things like academic instruction, in-service training, specialized training, and group gatherings. These activities are carried out both within and outside of the classroom, and advisors take part in them in order to progress their careers, learn information and skills, or enhance their own knowledge and abilities. In addition to this, they take part in training opportunities offered in the classroom and during in-service training, as well as corporate learning initiatives such as conferences and seminars oriented towards the requirements of educators. A considerable number of respondents said that they have advanced significantly in their efforts to include their workforce in a variety of corporate learning activities. The last category of support for career development was spoken by school administrators, who said that they were interested in and promoted the career development of their workers in order to establish a constructive learning environment. This was the final

CURRENT SCIENCE

category of support for career development. The vast majority of respondents were of the opinion that it is very important to encourage teachers to pursue postgraduate study and to act as a good example for other people working in the teaching profession. The majority of those who participated in the poll listed this as the key reason for pursuing an advanced degree.

There are seven distinct categories that make up mentoring duties, as well as mentoring roles in the process of developing a learning culture. Some roles that may be performed include being a learning resource, playing a collaborative role, offering feedback, sharing social capital, acting as a role model, playing a part in the process of growth, playing a cultural role, and providing intellectual stimulation.

One of the functions of a learning resource is to increase communication with trainees by ensuring that proper language is used and that information and skills are provided. Administrators routinely collaborate with one another to exchange information on a wide range of subjects, including the teaching profession, education and training, legal and official communications, and more. They consistently better themselves by taking part in research and assisting staff in meeting the standards that have been set for them. This content is geared for educators and provides them with the chance to investigate other points of view via their participation in the activities.

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